

Teaching English by basing on pedagogical technologies.

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Annotation

This article discusses about using pedagogical technologies in teaching English. Additionally, throughout this article, it is given some information about using technologies in today's world.

Key words:

Pedagogical technologies, education, educational programs, requirements, devices, modern pedagogy, education system, quality of education, multimedia programs.

Today, improving the quality, efficiency of education as well as raising common demands have become one of the unchanged movements of state policy, this is being common issue which is faced by a modern pedagogue. At the time, the rapidly improving areas of science, technology and production require enhancing the quality of education to a new level by means of content in the continuous education system.

The progress which is made in education growing young generation, forming them as intelligent mature, independent, and fulfilling specialists in all fields, and also training teachers who work loyally for their profession, of course, depends on a continuing education process. It is hardly secret is that the quality as well as effectiveness of education relies on the quality of the education which is provided.

Therefore, to improve the quality of education, we must always work on our own, besides conducting new researches. In order to design educational process is necessary to identify the content of education, educational aim, expected results, select the right way of teaching, forms, and devices, stimulate specific criteria for evaluating the knowledge of students, skills, and qualifications in advance, it is needed to pay attention to their correct implementation and harmony with one another in the time which is allocated.

The overall pedagogical and didactic requirements for all types of education is to raise the efficiency of work which does independently on the basis of the students' knowledge of programming, imagination and skills to stimulate their interests in scientific thinking, and also academic subjects to approach deep their professional knowledge, through both theoretical and practical training includes increasing their activity.

Basing on these requirements, subjects which are related to cutting-edge information technologies were involved the curriculum of the system of the education, their model

curricula were improved ,approved , and implemented by the Ministry of both Higher and Secondary special Education of The Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today,multimedia programs ,modern pedagogical technologies,and modern way of teaching are commonly used in the progress of the education.Preserving the form of traditional lessons in the previous teaching methods, while immersing the students in these lessons in ways that make active the students ' activities is the reason for the improvement in the level of learning of the learners.

It should be noted is that language is never unchanged ,it is always being changeable ,and developable .So, every applicant who is learning a foreign language, especially, English ought to work on his own outside of class ,make an improvement in his vocabulary,read lots of national literature and foreign literature ,additionally ,learn how to translate independently.

That is why, while translating small materials bilaterally from English into Uzbek,or else ,from Uzbek into English, he learns the mistakes which he makes and works independently on his drawbacks .

In resent years , educational programs which are ready - made have appeared on the internet, these programs may motivate students to learn foreign languages in terms of powerful interest.

For instance, when English language lessons are taught in computer classrooms, students not only being attracted to electronic textbooks,but also the phonetic exercises of the new word which they are learning, various expressions ,grammatical sentences are being heard and accepted by students which in turn, it means is that another opportunity to master the language well.At the age of computer has significantly made with ease the work of teachers ,and also lessons based on cutting -edge technologies are being properly organized is the reason for using of the time efficiently.

Today's youth are very energetic,and depending on their opinion, knowledge of information technologies and the experience of teachers,it needs to keep creating new electric programs and books in English that meet the time requirements.Now,there is no problem for teachers to prepare didactic visual aids,audio -materials ,and handouts.

In order to reach an achievement in the intended results,it is essential to further enhance the process of the education,that is way ,in today's education,it needs to create new content ,form ,as well as methods,to use both modern pedagogical and information technologies effectively,to use diveces like distance learning, electronic communication,and also electronic library.

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